

ANALYSIS OF CARBON-GLASS HYBRID FIBRE COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

A finite element modeling was developed to investigate the effect of the fiber hybridization on the mechanical properties of Carbon-Glass hybrid laminated composite plate. The FE analysis of hybrid composite plate is carried out to study the different mechanical behavior such as, stress, eigen-value buckling, modal, harmonic response, tensile and failure analysis using the ANSYS software. From the analysis, it is informed that the strength is increased when the carbon fiber is placed within the matrix material. The parametric study is also done by varying the aspect ratio and thickness ratio to see the effect. Finally, the applications of this advanced composite material have been discussed and reported.

Index Terms- Hybrid Composite, Mechanical Behaviors, ANSYS Software, Finite Element

I. INTRODUCTION

Hybrid composite materials are slowly replacing the conventional materials nowadays because of the merits they offer such as light-weight, high stiffness, high corrosion resistance, high durability. The hybrid composite materials can be made by selection of the suitable combination of fiber layers and resin. It consists of double or multiple woven fabric materials with different properties combined to make a superior material with the properties of both. Most widely used composite materials constitute concrete used in various engineering applications and also naturally formed composites as wood. The reinforced fiber provides the required strength when combined with the matrix resin. Fiber reinforced composite materials are widely used in various industries where the light weight is concerned. Due to its tailor-made properties, this type of material is used in automobile, aerospace, civil and energy industries. During the operation in such industries, the material is subjected to both static and dynamic load in harsh environment. Hence the researchers are interested to analyses the stress, tensile and failure behaviour, eigen value buckling, modal and harmonic response of the laminated hybrid composite materials for the design purpose.

II. RELATED WORKS

Experimental investigation was carried out to study the mechanical strength of glass-carbon fiber reinforced vinyl ester resin composites. The fabricated samples of ASTM standard are subjected for the tensile tests, compression tests, flexural tests to determine its mechanical properties [1]. The bending and free vibration behaviour of thin-to-moderately thick composite plates reinforced by single-walled carbon nanotubes are studied using the FEM based on the first-order shear deformation plate theory with different boundary conditions.

Numerical illustrations are computed by an in-house finite element code and shows a good agreement with the solutions obtained by the FE commercial package ANSYS [2]. Experimental studies are carried out under both tensile and compressive in-plane quasi-static loading to find out the mechanical properties of two types of hybrid composites (8H satin weave T300 carbon fabrics and plain weave E-glass fabrics with epoxy resin). It is observed that, placing glass fabric layers in the exterior and carbon fabric layers in the interior gives higher tensile strength and ultimate tensile strain than placing carbon fabric layers in the exterior and glass fabric layers in the interior [3]. Furthermore, the experimental and numerical investigation on parametric study of vibration and buckling characteristics of industry driven woven fiber Glass-Carbon/epoxy hybrid composite panels was carried out. The effects of lamination sequence on the natural frequencies of vibration and buckling strength of the hybrid panels were studied in this investigation [4]. The experimental results are compared with the numerical predictions using the FEM based software package ANSYS 13.0. A very good agreement was observed between the experimental and ANSYS results.

III. TECHNOLOGY USED

In ANSYS ACP have two modes, such as pre-processing mode and post processing. In the pre-processing mode, all composite definitions are created and applied to the geometry (FE mesh). The input parameters file of the composite materials are applied to the FE model and then solved. In the post-processing mode, complete solution is done and then the import the result file(s). In post processing failure, safety, strains and stresses results are obtained. To combine fabrics into a non-crimp fabric, the stack-up sequence is used. Rosettes coordinate systems are used to set the reference direction of oriented element sets. Point should lie inside or close to the reference surface to give the correct results. The properties of resin epoxy, epoxy glass and epoxy carbon woven (230 Gpa) prepreg taken from the reference [1] has been used in the present analysis. The composite orientation and the composite view layer by layer are shown in the Figure 1 (a, b), respectively.

Figure 1. (a) Composite Orientation, (b) Composite view layer by layer.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION AND RESULTS

The numerical analysis of hybrid composite laminate is carried out using the first order shear deformation theory (FSDT) by using the ANSYS software. Thicknesses of carbon and glass fibers are taken as 1mm and 2mm, respectively and orientation of composite plate of carbon-glass-carbon (C-G-C) sequence is taken as [90/0/0]. The dimension of composite plate is taken as: $150 \times 80 \times 40$, mm³.

1. Results and analysis

• *Eigen value buckling*

The failure associated with buckling usually happens in the first mode itself but the buckled shape can be sustained in higher modes, $[K_E + \lambda K_S] [\varphi] = 0$

Where, K_E = elastic stiffness matrix. K_s = stress stiffness matrix, λ = eigen value, ϕ = eigen vector which illustrates the buckled mode shape.

For finding out the buckling load, eigen value is multiplied with the initial load, $N = \lambda \times N_{x0}$
 Where, N = buckling critical load, N_{x0} = applied forces, λ = critical eigen value.

- *Eigen value buckling by increasing number of layers*

Now by keeping the composite thickness same and increasing a layer of CE either from top or bottom sides with the scheme of CE-CE-GE-CE-CE as 0.5, 0.5, 2, 0.5, 0.5 mm the corresponding mode shapes are obtained. Figure 2 shows the Mode shapes for buckling by increasing layers.

Figure 2. Mode shapes for buckling by increasing layers.

- *Eigen value buckling by varying thickness ratio (a/h)*

Taking $a/h = 25$, the first 10 mode shapes are found shown in Table 1 and observed that with increase of thickness the corresponding frequency increases.

Table 1. Mode shapes for buckling for $a/h = 25$

	Mode number										
		1st	2nd	3rd	4th	5th	6th	7th	8th	9th	10th
Load multiplier (e5)		3.295	4.117	4.972	5.862	6.993	8.206	9.365	9.477	9.982	10.325

- **Modal Analysis**

Here the first 10 natural frequencies of composite plate and the mode shape are obtained by fixing the plate at one end (CFFF), are shown in Table 2. Figure 3 shows the total deformation corresponding to first four nodes.

Table 2. Natural frequencies of composite plate for CFFF condition

	Mode number									
	1st	2nd	3rd	4th	5th	6th	7th	8th	9th	10th
Frequency(Hz)	170.87	618.34	1055.7	2022.8	2469.5	2892.3	3779.9	3932.6	4926.3	5502.6

Figure 3. Total deformation corresponding to first four nodes.

- *Modal Analysis by varying aspect ratio (a/b)*

From the Table 3, it can be seen that with the change of mode, the frequency increases and by increase of aspect ratio frequency value decrease. It is because of that stiffness of composite plate decreased with increase of length.

Table 3. Natural frequencies of composite plate by varying aspect ratio

a/b	Frequency (Hz)				
	Mode number				
	1st	2nd	3rd	4th	5th
2.5	96.21	445.38	598.1	1419.8	1516.1
5	24.074	150.56	209.65	420.24	421.28

● **Harmonic Response**

By fixing the composite plate at both the ends (CFCF), its mode shape changes and frequency value increases as 1064, 1541, 2852 and 3538 Hertz, respectively with the mode. When giving load at middle of plate of 250N and damping factor of 0.02. The maximum amplitude using cluster result was found to be 2.319mm. Table 4 shows the first five natural frequencies of composite plate by varying aspect ratio, such as a/b=2.5, 3.0 and 5.0, respectively.

Figure 4. Frequency response with both end fixed.

● **Harmonic analysis by varying aspect ratio (a/b)**

Table 4. Natural frequencies of composite plate by varying aspect ratio

a/b	Frequency (Hz)				
	Mode number				
	1st	2nd	3rd	4th	5th
2.5	604.75	1039.5	1640.3	2303.5	3150.7
3	421.71	822.26	1149.3	1782.7	2220.7
5	152.73	419.25	447.46	817.47	927.05

● **Bending Test**

Bending test is done with simply supported with concentrated load all over the length. With applying force, we can find out Inverse Reverse Factor (IRF) with the help of composite failure. So we can find out bending diagram of deformation and stress by applying 5000N load. At top layer max stress is 466.53MPa and min stress is 7.3221MPa, at core max stress is 27.767 MPa and min stress is 0.1925 MPa, at bottom Layer max stress is 466.38 MPa and min stress is 25.177 MPa.

Max deformation is -0.01028mm and min deformation is -8.9071mm

Bending stress diagram of top path max stress is 459.93 MPa

Bending stress diagram of neutral layer at which middle of length stress is zero

● **Bending test by increasing number of layers**

Bending test is done with simply supported with concentrated load all over the length. With applying force, we can find out Inverse Reverse Factor (IRF) with the help of composite

failure. Applying 5000N load, it is observed that the inverse reverse factor turns out to be greater than 1; the material is prone to failure. However the material failure occurs in a force much below it, 3000N turned out to be the safe limit. At Bottom most layer maximum and minimum stresses developed are 226.44 MPa and 2.644 MPa respectively. At Bottom layer maximum and minimum stresses developed are 87.593 MPa and 4.7426 MPa respectively. At Core layer maximum and minimum stresses developed are 28.242 MPa and 5.389 MPa respectively. At Top layer maximum and minimum stresses developed are 87.307 MPa and 4.777 MPa respectively. At Top most layer maximum and minimum stresses developed are 226.52 MPa and 2.7142 MPa respectively. Max deformation developed is : 3.0221e-17mm, Min deformation developed is : -1.3661mm.

Tensile Test

The specimen was created in ANSYS design modeler geometry. Applying fixed support at one end and remote displacement of 0.2mm at another end. Following figure shows the deformation on tensile test specimen and stress distribution on bottom, top and core layers.

From images we can see that the max stress, max strain and total deformation of whole body are 118.13 MPa, 0.0023684 and 0.20053 mm, respectively. By checking ply-wise the tensile stress at bottom, core and top layer was found to be 113.29 MPa, 66.244 MPa and 5.131 MPa respectively.

V. CONCLUSION

The proposed approach applies computer vision methodology that is flexible, sound act in real time performance. The use of ANSYS Workbench and ANSYS ACP Pre and Post Processing is very much agreeable with the results obtained. The stresses generated in laminate using ANSYS and stress which are calculated by normal empirical formulae are similar enough to justify the present results. The failure analysis of the laminate gave first ply failure and last ply failure load of the laminate. Considering the results obtained in whole analysis, the following inferences can be made.

- Laminates containing the number of lamina, different orientation, and different materials can be analyzed using ANSYS.
- The stresses which are evaluated are useful to carryout failure analysis and determine the characteristic properties of material of the laminate.
- The tensile test was done for layers and stresses were determined.
- The natural frequency of composite and harmonic response was also determined.
- The stress developed per fibre significantly reduced by increasing the thickness of plate.

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